

LINGUOSTATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF SIDQIY XONDAYLIQIY'S GHAZAL WITH THE RADIF "MENGA"

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Abstract: This article presents a linguostatistical analysis of Sidqiy Xondayliqiy's ghazal with the radif "Menga." Lexical units expressing independent meaning and those lacking independent meaning are classified according to parts of speech. The study also determines whether the units belong to the native or borrowed lexical layer.

Keywords: literary text, linguostatistics, parts of speech, word structure, native layer, borrowed layer.

To determine the structure of any literary work, the status of its units, and interlingual relations, the use of linguostatistical analysis methods yields positive results. Considering this, it is particularly relevant to study early 20th-century literature, a period marked by significant linguistic and semantic changes. With this in mind, it was decided to conduct a linguostatistical analysis of Sidqiy Xondayliqiy's ghazal with the radif "Menga."

"In recent years, statistics has been widely applied in linguistics as in other fields, and this method has come to be known as linguostatistics. The application of the statistical method in linguistics is not an end in itself, but rather a tool used alongside traditional methods to understand the extremely complex structure of language and the secrets of its functioning." Linguist S. Rizayev notes that in modern world linguistics there are three stages in identifying language phenomena:

1. Statistical observation or calculation: recording data to obtain precise information about the phenomenon under study;
2. Systematization of numerical data: organizing, grouping, and arranging the collected data in a specific order;
3. Analysis: clarifying the essential content of the results obtained in the second stage and providing their quantitative description.

During the statistical analysis, attention was paid to the following:

1. All independent words were included (nouns in their base form and verbs in the infinitive form).
2. Compound, paired, and reduplicated words were treated as single lexical units.

3. Units without independent lexical meaning were identified separately.

In Sidqiy Xondayliqiy's ghazal with the radif "Menga," a total of 70 words (including repetitions) were used. These units can be statistically analyzed as follows:

1) **Nouns:** falak (fate/sky), farog'at (comfort), o'rin (place), mehnat (labor), sharofat (honor), razolat (baseness), el (people), shafolat (intercession), furumoya (ignoble person), hasrat (sorrow), do'st (friend), hamiyat (zeal), bosh (head), fazl (virtue), qadr-u qimmat (value and dignity), shodliq (joy), yuz (face), riqqat (tenderness), ro'z (day), oyina/oyna (mirror), safo (purity), fil (elephant), illat (illness/fault), suxanvarliq (eloquence), dil (heart), Sidqiy, shuhrat (fame), rohat (comfort);

2) **Adjective:** yangi (new);

3) **Numeral:** bir (one);

4) **Pronouns:** ne (what), men (I – used 10 times), oni (him/her/it), ne bo'lmoq (what to be), alar (they), nechuk (how), bu (this);

5) **Verbs:** yetgay (may reach), berur (gives), arjumand bo'lmoq (to become honorable), ko'rmoq (to see), yetmaslik (not to reach), vafo ko'rmaslik (not to see loyalty), balo bo'lmoq (to become a calamity), ko'rmaslik (not to see), bilmam (I do not know), so'rmoq/so'ramoq (to ask);

6) **Adverbs:** dame (for a moment – used twice), zarracha (a little);

7) **Units without independent lexical meaning:**

a) Negative word: yo'q (no – used three times);

b) Auxiliary verb: erkan (was/is apparently);

c) Copular form: erur (is/means "to be");

d) Subordinating conjunction: magar (perhaps/unless);

e) Modal word: darig'oki (alas);

f) Particles: chu, ki (used twice).

In the literary text, the unit "bir" functions not as a numeral but as a demonstrative meaning "such."

1. Structural Analysis of the Nouns

-**Simple root nouns:** falak, farog'at, o'rin, mehnat, sharofat, razolat, el, shafolat, furumoya, hasrat, do'st, hamiyat, bosh, fazl, qadr-u qimmat, yuz, riqqat, ro'z, oyina, safo, fil, illat, dil, shuhrat, rohat. Among these, units such as o'rin, el, yuz, ko'z belong to the Common Turkic lexical stock.

-**Derived nouns:** shodliq, suxanvarliq, Sidqiy. Although "shod" and "suxan" are Persian words, they are considered part of the native layer due to the addition of Turkic suffixes. The pen name "Sidqiy" contains the Arabic root "sidq" and the Arabic suffix "-iy," and is therefore considered a borrowed unit.

Other Parts of Speech

- The only adjective used, “yangi,” belongs to the native lexical layer.
- The numeral “bir” is also a Common Turkic lexeme.
- All pronouns listed (ne, men, bu, oni, alar, nechuk, etc.) are Common Turkic units belonging to the native layer, though some represent archaic or altered forms.

Verbs:

- Simple root verbs (yetgay, berur, ko‘rmoq, yetmaslik, ko‘rmaslik, bilmam, so‘rmoq) are Common Turkic.
- Compound verbs (arjumand bo‘lmoq, vafo ko‘rmaslik, balo bo‘lmoq) include Arabic and Persian lexemes, but since they also contain Common Turkic elements, they are regarded as belonging to the native layer.

Of the adverbs, “dame” is borrowed, while “zarracha” belongs to the native layer.

Among the function words, “yo‘q,” “erkan,” and “erur” are Common Turkic; “magar,” “darig‘oki,” “chu,” and “ki” belong to the borrowed layer.

Conclusion: The linguostatistical analysis of the poem shows that nouns and verbs constitute the majority of lexical units. Adjectives and adverbs are used sparingly, while pronouns occur frequently due to repetition.

References:

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